
Do stars smile back at us? Calculating photocenter shifts for fictional spot configurations based on stellar personalities

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Abstract

Light decrement caused by stellar spots can have a significant effect on our observations of distant stars, since it causes the photocenter of the point source to shift. The degree of these photocenter shifts highly depends on the configuration of the dark starspots. Starspots appear where magnetic flux tubes pierce through the photosphere and through the interaction of plasma and magnetic field, suppress convective energy transport. However, other factors might have an impact on the final positions. One of the factors we looked into are personalities and possible emotions of the stars. In this work, we created fictional surface temperature maps of starspot configurations corresponding to different personalities, beliefs and emotional ranges a star might have. We calculated the photocenter shifts of these maps to see how this anthropomorphic approach fits to observation.

1 Introduction

Getting information about the surface of far away stars is not an easy task. Since stars are point sources, direct observations of their surfaces are not possible. However, with indirect methods, like Doppler imaging it is possible to get a temperature map of our targets.

Stars with high magnetic activity produce star spots in a significant size that might affect our parallax measurements. Since spots are colder, therefore darker, they cause light-decrement and shift the observed "center" of the star. As the star rotates, the photocenter of the star shifts in different degrees as time passes. This can introduce an uncertainty in parallax measurements.

The other key question this work focuses on is the personality and possible emotions of stars. Most astronomers try to find the answer for the following questions: How far the stars are? What spectral class are they? How old are they? But there is a significant question that has never been asked before: How are the stars? If we have a thought experiment that the different spot configurations reflect not only the magnetic activity, but also emotional properties of the stars, we can see that the size of the photocenter shifts might rely on the personal well-being, emotional state, or beliefs of the targets.

In this work we present multiple fictional spot configurations corresponding to different stellar personalities. We also calculate the possible photocenter shifts for each case and then compare them to see, which personality causes the more displacement of the point source.

2 Methods

2.1 Drawing the maps

To create the surface temperature maps we used our own IDL program called `drawmap`. In its interactive GUI, maps can easily drawn be as a form of "pixelart" by changing the temperature of each square. As a result we get the surface temperatures in each unit as an input file for our Doppler imaging code, which we will not use here at all. We used a $6^\circ \times 6^\circ$ grid (except of the UwU star where we used $10^\circ \times 10^\circ$ – note that emotions are not quantifiable, therefore, there is no need for any sort of consistency or

Figure 1. The GUI of drawmap in the case of the Gyula star.

rigorous scientific approach) and set the effective temperature to $T_{\text{eff}} = 5000$ K for each map. It is an easy number to remember. The interface of the program can be seen at Fig. 1.

2.2 Calculating the photocenters

To calculate the photocenter shifts we used our own code written in Python3. We have used the following packages: `numpy`, `matplotlib`, `astropy`, `pandas` and `cartopy`. The algorithm operates by structuring temperature data into a matrix-style `pandas` DataFrame, organized by stellar latitude and longitude. Utilizing the `cartopy` library, the code maps this distribution onto an orthogonal coordinate system to generate an orthographic projection of the star at a specific rotational phase. By extracting the projected temperature data and transformed coordinates, the script calculates a temperature-weighted mean for each coordinate cell. This result defines the specific position of the shifted photocenter for that phase. To model the dynamical shift, the process is repeated across 180 distinct rotational phases. This sequence generates a characteristic curve illustrating the photocenter's "motion" as varying spot distributions rotate into view. Finally, the code identifies the two most distant points on this trajectory to calculate the maximum photocenter displacement, measured in milliarcseconds (mas).

For the calculations we used the distance and radius of the star first came into our mind, LQ Hydrae. We like LQ Hydrae. The exact values are $d = 18.35$ pc and $R = 0.97 R_{\odot}$. We chose different inclinations for each map depending on our subjective opinion, mood, and the spot locations on the surface. The inclination values are listed in Table 1.

Name of the map	i [°]
UwU	70
Happy	70
Pacal	60
Gyula	90
Beni	100 (do not ask questions)

Table 1. Inclination values used to calculate the photocenter shift for each map

Figure 2. Mercator projection of the UwU star

Figure 3. Orthographic projection of the UwU star

3 Created maps and personalities

In this section we present the fictional spot configuration we have studied and explain their personality traits. These maps go by the following nicknames: **UwU**, **Happy**, **Pacal**, **Gyula**, **Beni**. On the Mercator projections the x axis stands for the longitude- while the y axis stands for the latitude degrees. Not that you can actually read the axis titles.

3.1 The UwU star

This spot configuration is known for its peaceful, satisfied demeanor also radiating "cute vibes", as experts might say. It is a temperature map of a star aware of its effect on others. They might take advantage of it. The Mercator projection of the map is shown at Fig 2, while the orographical map can be seen at Fig 3.

Figure 4. Mercator projection of the Happy star

Figure 5. Orthographic projection of the Happy star

3.2 The Happy star

It is just a chill, happy little fella. This map shows positive emotions, looks like a star who is just glad to be here. It can easily socialise and brings joy to the others around it. It attracts the company of others – an effect directly proportional to its joy and inversely proportional to the square of the distance between those involved. The Mercator projection of the map is shown at Fig 4, while the orthographical map can be seen at Fig 5.

3.3 The Pacal star

Now this configuration is giving us a hard statement based on its belief. The word "pacal" is the Hungarian word for tripe. Since tripe stew is a widely spread, yet somewhat controversial Hungarian dish – its culinary value is a topic of debate even for the authors – , this star has a clear opinion on what its favorite food is. The Mercator projection of the map is shown at Fig 6, while the orthographical map can be seen at Fig 7.

Figure 8. Mercator projection of the Gyula star

Figure 9. Orthographical projection of the Gyula star

3.4 The Gyula star

Gyula is a configuration which is heavily invested into politics, has very biased opinions on the world and shares them with everyone aggressively. This type of star can make everything about local politics and annoy everyone and everything around it. Experts also call it "weird guy". The Mercator projection of the map is shown at Fig 8, while the orthographical map can be seen at Fig 9.

3.5 The Beni star

This configuration is the complete opposite of the Gyula star: it is calm, considered and silent. It also has clear opinions but most of time it does not show them. It radiates authority, and others are usually highly appreciative of this kind of personality. Experts also call it as "small blue guy". The Mercator projection of the map is shown at Fig 10, while the orthographical map can be seen at Fig 11.

Figure 10. Mercator projection of the Beni star

Figure 11. Orthographical projection of the Beni star

4 Results

We have calculated the photocenter shifts for each configuration using the Python3 code explained in Section 2. The values for the shifts are shown in Table 2. The photocenter curve diagrams can be seen at Fig 12. These are more or less our quantifiable results. Emotions are subjective and qualitative,

Name of the star	Photocenter shift [mas]
UwU	0.004340029496965441 mas
Happy	0.005717882477174124 mas
Pacal	0.004987982310686638 mas
Gyula	0.006237775332235912 mas
Beni	0.00934024738813026 mas

Table 2. The calculated photocenter shifts for each map

hence these values cannot be correlated with the personalities, emotions and mood of our target star. Which is too bad, we really wanted to do some math. For a qualitative and subjective analysis, see the next section.

5 Discussion

We draw the conclusion that stars with more complex emotional range and more developed personality have higher photocenter shift value. This means that the effect of the light decrement is not dependent on the kind of the emotion the star might feel, but more on the range of variability of these feelings. The shift value might have linear dependency on the vehemence of the emotions of each star. This means, that the stronger emotions cause higher photocenter shift. So we can conclude that although the Beni star (which has the highest value for the shift) might look nonchalant at first glance, it indeed has really strong, deep emotional world. This theory needs further investigation in the future.

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References

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(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 12. Photocenter curves of the different maps

Figure 13. An example of tripe stew with pork leg (csülkös pacalpörkölt). Source: [2]

Appendix

Gyula and Beni are characters from the Hungarian animated YouTube series, *Weird happenings at Szondi street* (Különös történések a Szondi utcában) created by Levente Roznár [1]. Tripe stew (pacal pörkölt, see Fig 13.) is one of the best Hungarian dishes and there is no bias from the author in this statement at all.